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ABOUT SOME METHODS OF TEACHING LATIN IN MEDICAL HIGHER
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstracts: This article describes the methodology of teaching Latin as the main language of the medical branch. About the role of the Latin language in medical higher education. On the effectiveness of teaching Latin by an integrated method with other subjects. An example of declension in Latin of nouns with adjectives in comparison with the Uzbek language is also given.

Key words: education, Latin, medical, terminology, term, medical terminology, learning, institution.

Among all subjects taught in higher medical educational institutions, Latin is of particular importance. Today in our Samarkand State medical university Latin is not listed as a foreign language or any other language, but is a separate part of normal and topographic human anatomy, and in this regard, the discipline of the Latin language occupies a special place among the physiological and anatomical sciences. The methodology of teaching Latin is not similar to the methodology of teaching exact and humanitarian disciplines, a special approach is needed to teaching this subject, because no one speaks this language today.

First of all, it is necessary to interest students in this discipline, to discover new features of this subject day after day, to tell them what an important place it has in their future profession. In this, the orthographically correct spelling of each part of a person comes out in the first place. To implement the above-mentioned methods of teaching this discipline is necessary. Based on my many years of experience in this field, I will share with readers my most acceptable skills and practices.

Today, teaching Latin in medical higher educational institutions has become an integral part of medicine, since all diagnoses of patients, prescribing and writing prescriptions are undoubtedly carried out in Latin. Since, according to the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan dated April 1, 2022, on the establishment of Samarkand state medical university and further improvement of personnel training system in the field, the requirements for teaching disciplines have intensified, serious views have been acquired on the training of future doctors and healthcare specialists. At the same time, the Latin language course is an important part of medical education. Currently,

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Latin is being studied at a medical higher educational institution at the faculties of medicine, pediatrics, dentistry, medical prevention, medical biology, folk medicine, pharmacy, higher nursing etc.

It can be said that Latin has become the main language along with other languages of the university. Students get acquainted with the basics of medical terminology for the successful continuation of training in the specialties of medicine. The purpose of the teaching methodology of Latin is to explain in an accessible, simple language to students in an integrated method with other subjects: for example, with Uzbek, Russian, English, French and German, anatomy, physiology, the basics of public health protection, which are conducted at our university.

The main task of the teaching methodology of the Latin language is to form professional competence in medical terminology among students, mastering the basics of the Latin language, which gives them the opportunity to read, write and translate correctly, as well as explain the essence of the text. In the process of teaching Latin, interdisciplinary teaching methods are implemented that improve the perception and memorization of medical terms among students, this integrated method of teaching Latin performs both general education and educational tasks.

As you know, general education tasks include enriching the vocabulary of Greek-Latin origin, expanding horizons in the field of medical terminology, developing logical thinking, and of course, improving the medical culture of students. The educational objectives of the integrated method of teaching Latin are to introduce students to the history of the emergence of the Latin language, its content and essence, the role of the development of world culture and science. With the integrated method of teaching Latin, it is very convenient to coordinate a calendar-thematic plan: for example, in Latin, the fourth lesson, if the declension of nouns, then in English, Russian and Uzbek, too, so that the declension of nouns takes place — in this case it will be easy to perceive and remember. Nouns in Latin are divided into five declensions, depending on the final sounds of the base, in accordance with belonging to a particular declension, they take different case endings. And in the Russian language the same thing, there are three main declensions, and in the Uzbek and English languages the same thing, there is one main declensions.

Accordingly, in Latin, the first declension includes nouns and adjectives, the basis of which ends in -a; therefore, it can also be called the declension -a. Feminine nouns belong to it, which are in nom. sing. have the ending -a, in gen. sing. - ae, e.g.: schola, scholae - school, schools; villa, villae - villa, villas. This also includes a small

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group of masculine nouns denoting a male profession or belonging to a particular nationality (the natural sign associated with the meaning of the word is decisive); for example: poēta, poētae - poet; agricōla, agricōlae - farmer; Persa, Persae - Persian. Imagine, and in Uzbek and English, too, the nouns of masculine, feminine and general genders with the ending -a, -ī belong to the first declension. This matching method gives students a good opportunity to memorize the topics they are studying. Here is an example of declension: Nominativus beautiful girl -puellā pulchrā, good friend -amīcā bonā. Genetivus beautiful girl -puellae pulchrae, good friend -amīcae bonae, Dativus beautiful girl -puellae pulchrae, good friend -amīcae bonae, Accusativus beautiful girl -puellam pulchram, good friend -amīcam bonam, Ablativus beautiful girl -puellā pulchrā -a good friend -amīcā bonā. In the same way, Latin can be taught by the method of intersubject communication with other subjects.

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